

Global Symbiosis of wisdom: the Indian Knowledge system

Dr. Prashant Bhimsen Pagare
Head, Department of Education
Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University,
Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar,(MS) India

India has a rich history of knowledge dissemination and education with Ancient teaching from Vedic Philosophy, Buddhist Philosophy and Jain Philosophy and more traditional. The development of the education system in ancient India, The Gurukul system, Takshashila and Nalanda University were influential centers that contributed to the spread of knowledge, fostering innovation, truth, peace, and the practice of yoga , particularly in institutions like Takshashila University, was make by a multidisciplinary approach. Students were exposed to a diverse range of subjects, including philosophy, science, arts, and politics. The gurukul system emphasized personalized mentorship, fostering holistic development .Nalanda University played key role in advancing knowledge, attracting scalars from different parts of the world

The emphasis on truth, peace, and the practice of yoga not only enriched mind but also cultivated a spirit of harmony and self discovery. The gurukul system with its personalized mentorship, nurtured not just scholars but well-rounded individuals ready to contribute to society

As we delve into the past, let us draw inspiration from these timeless principles to inform and shape the future of education. Global community can learn from the inclusivity, interdisciplinary focus and commitment to values that defined India's ancient educational institutions. As we reflect on this rich heritage, let us recognize India's historical role as a vishvaguru and contemplate how these principles can guide us in navigating the complexities of our modern world.